

Local Government in Spain

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments

5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Spain: An Introduction

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General Framework of Intergovernmental Relations

Despite the fact that in the Spanish political system municipalities precede the creation of other territorial entities (i.e. autonomous communities), their sphere of competences is decided by the laws of the state and, to a lesser extent of the autonomous communities. The Spanish Constitution (Article 137) establishes the principle of local autonomy although with no further specification or delimitation of competences.

This top-down configuration of the local autonomy affects not only the competences of municipalities but also the intergovernmental relationships, both horizontal cooperation among municipalities and vertical coordination and cooperation between municipalities and other territorial entities (provinces, autonomous communities and the state).

The horizontal cooperation between municipalities is frequently channeled by the creation of single-purpose entities (i.e. the so-called *mancomunidades* or commonwealths) to provide public services, most frequently those related to environmental and social policies (e.g. waste management, social assistance). The Law of the Basis of the Local System (LBRL) of 1985 establishes formal requirements in the process of constitution of *mancomunidades*, leaving municipalities to define the scope and internal organization (Article 44 LBRL).

As for the vertical intergovernmental relationships, the LBRL refers to the principle of 'institutional loyalty' by which each level of government (state, regional and local) is supposed to cooperate with the others and not interfere in the legitimate exercise of other levels' competences. Therefore, vertical cooperation is understood as administrative assistance without compromising each level of government's competence. The cooperation between levels of government is made on a voluntary basis. In addition, upper levels of government (the state and the regions) may coordinate the action of municipalities to guarantee coherence and according to the subsidiarity principle (Article 58 and 59 LBRL).

Control and Supervision of the Local Government

Generally speaking, the Spanish current local government system includes very limited supervision or control on municipal and provincial activity by the state and the autonomous communities. The Constitutional Court has ruled that the local autonomy principle under the Spanish Constitution (Article 137) excludes governmental controls to a great extent. The LBRL replaces state and regional controls on local governments with a complex system of intergovernmental relations based on the idea of full respect for the powers of local

jurisdictions and the principle of cooperation. Basically, the LBRL establishes legal instruments to prevent conflicts between state and autonomous communities on one hand, and local authorities on the other, while obliging local governments to share information with supra-local authorities. To prevent or resolve conflicts of authority, the law promotes the 'free cooperation' of public administrations, either in the form of agreements or by participation in collaborative bodies, and by encouraging local level administrations to participate in the decision-making processes.

The most important control on the local governments is performed by the judicial branch (i.e. administrative courts). The inter-administrative litigation regarding local issues is abundant. All municipalities and provinces must communicate the decisions and by-laws adopted to the autonomous communities and the state. In case of infringement, both the autonomous communities and the state may require local governments to accommodate local decisions to the laws, or alternatively and directly bring the case before the administrative courts. The judicial proceedings deal with the legal correctness of local authorities' decisions and not with the political opportunity or necessity of adopting specific measures at the local level.

Despite the fact that local government action is controlled through the judicial branch of the government, there are also some cases of administrative supervision by regional or state authorities, as directly foreseen by sector-specific laws. This is the case of land use and urban planning policy where the approval of municipal land use plans requires the regional government's approval. This type of supervision is usually channeled through cooperative administrative procedures.

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